

The Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Aliphatic Aldehydes by Acid Permanganate

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The rate of the oxidation of formaldehyde and chloroacetaldehydes by acid permanganate, in the presence of fluoride ions, is of first order with respect to the aldehyde, the oxidant and hydrogen ions. The activation parameters have been evaluated. The oxidation fails to induce the polymerisation of acrylonitrile. The rate of oxidation is influenced by polar substituents and the reaction constant ρ^* is -1.32 ± 0.05 at 25°. The results are discussed in terms of a mechanism involving rate determining removal of a hydride ion from the aldehyde hydrate.

In a preliminary communication¹ it was shown that acetaldehyde is oxidised by acid permanganate *via* its keto form and probably involves transfer of a hydride ion from the aldehyde to the oxidant. The oxidation showed a kinetic isotope effect confirming the rupture of a C-H bond. The present investigation was undertaken to substantiate the mechanism proposed earlier.

This paper reports the kinetics of some aliphatic aldehydes bearing electron withdrawing substituents and evaluates the reaction constant.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aldehydes were commercial products and purified either by distillation under reduced pressure, under an atmosphere of nitrogen or by repeated crystallisation.

All other details of experimental procedure have been described earlier¹.

RESULTS

Product Analysis : The main product of the oxidation of aldehyde is the corresponding carboxylic acid. It is observed that for every mole of permanganate consumed, nearly 2.45 mole of the carboxylic acid is formed (Table 1). The overall reaction may be written as follows

Rate Laws : When the aldehyde and hydrogen ions are in excess, the rate of disappearance of permanganate follows first order rate law. The reaction was followed under pseudo-first-order conditions by keeping a large excess of aldehyde ($\times 10$ or greater).

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The reaction is of first order in the aldehyde. Under the conditions of constant ionic strength, the order with respect to hydrogen ion is also unity. Some typical rate data are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 1

Product Analysis

R	[RCHO] $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ [H ⁺] $2.0 M$ [NaF] $0.05 M$				
	$10^4[\text{Acid}]M$	$10^4[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ moles/litre			
	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0
H	5.0	9.8	14.5	19.6	24.5
ClCH ₂	4.9	9.8	14.5	19.8	24.3
Cl ₂ CH	5.1	10.0	14.4	19.2	24.3
Cl ₃ C	4.8	9.9	14.6	19.5	24.4

TABLE 2

Oxidation of aldehydes, RCHO, by acid permanganate

R	[NaF] 0.01 Temp. 25°			
	$10^4[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ mol/l	[RCHO] mol/l	[H ⁺] mol/l	$k_1 \times 10^4$ sec ⁻¹
H	1.0	0.1	1.0	2.20
	1.0	0.5	1.0	11.10
	1.0	0.1	0.5†	1.43
	1.0	0.1	1.0†	2.80
	1.0	0.1	1.5†	4.30
ClCH ₂	1.0	0.2	1.0	1.00
	2.0	1.0	1.0	5.04
	1.0	0.2	0.5†	0.71
	1.0	0.2	1.0†	1.41
	1.0	0.2	2.0†	2.80
Cl ₂ CH	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.24
	1.0	4.0	1.0	1.00
	1.0	1.0	0.5†	0.30
	1.0	1.0	1.0†	0.60
	1.0	1.0	2.0†	1.27
CCl ₃	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.028
	1.0	8.0	1.0	0.22
	3.0	8.0	1.0	0.23
	1.0	4.0	0.5†	0.08
	1.0	4.0	1.0†	0.17
	1.0	4.0	2.0†	0.33

† Ionic Strength = $2.0 M$.

Test for free radical: The oxidation of these aldehydes, under nitrogen, does not induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile. Thus, it is unlikely that free radicals are formed in this reaction.

Effect of Temperature: Data on the effect of temperature on the reaction rate are summarized in Table 3. The specific rate constant, k is defined as $k = k_1/[\text{Aldehyde}][\text{H}^+]$.

The activation parameters are recorded in Table 4. The errors in the values of ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔF^* are ± 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹, ± 2 cal/mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ and ± 1.5 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively.

TABLE 3

Effect of Temperature on the reaction rate

[NaF] 0.01M

R	Temp. °C	10 ⁵ k (l ² mol ⁻² sec ⁻¹)				
		25	30	35	40	45
H		220	310	430	590	800
ClCH ₂		50	72.5	102	145	200
Cl ₂ CH		2.4	3.52	5.0	7.1	10
CCl ₃		0.28	0.42	0.60	0.90	1.26

TABLE 4

Activation Parameters

R	ΔH^* kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* cal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔF^* 25° kcal mol ⁻¹
H	12.3	-30	22.2
ClCH ₂	13.0	-31	22.8
Cl ₂ CH	13.2	-35	23.6
CCl ₃	14.1	-37	25.1

DISCUSSION

Permanganic acid is the most likely oxidising species in strong acid solution^{1,2}.

It has been shown that aliphatic aldehydes are oxidised by Cr(VI)³ and by bromine⁴ *via* their hydrates. The aldehydes studied here exist mostly as their hydrates in aqueous solution and hence either the aldehyde hydrate or its simple derivative is the most likely intermediate. Oxidation of acetaldehyde showed a kinetic isotope effect confirming the rupture of α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step.

Wiberg and Stewart⁵ suggested formation of a manganese ester followed by transfer of a proton to an external base in the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes. However, no general base catalysis was observed by the authors⁵ and ester formation is unlikely in view of equal ease of oxidation of diisopropyl ether and isopropanol⁶. Moreover, a reaction involving a

proton transfer in the rate-determining step should be facilitated by the introduction of electron-withdrawing groups. It is, however, observed that electron-withdrawing groups decrease the oxidation rate of aliphatic aldehydes and the results give good correlation in the Taft plot with a reaction constant $\rho^* = -1.32 \pm 0.05$ at 25° . The negative ρ^* value points to an electron deficient carbon centre in the transition state and strongly supports a hydride transfer mechanism in the acid permanganate oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes.

REFERENCES

1. K. K. Banerji, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1972, **27B**, 772.
2. K. K. Banerji and P. Nath, *Bull. chem. soc. Japan*, 1969, **42**, 2038.
3. C. Goswami and K. K. Banerji, *Bull. Chem. soc. Japan*, 1970, **43**, 2644.
4. B. G. Cox and P. T. McTigue, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 1210.
5. K. B. Wiberg and R. Stewart, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1786
6. R. M. Barter and J. S. Littler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (B), 1967, 205.